

Chemical Reactions under Electrodeless Discharge.

By

S. S. BHATNAGAR, RAMA KRISHNA SHARMA AND N. G. MITRA.

McVicker, Marsh and Stewart (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 642, 817, 2147 and subsequent papers) have studied the Tesla-luminiscence spectra of several organic substances and explained the importance of band and line spectra in bringing out the configuration of molecules in them. Recently, Bhatnagar, Shrivastava, Mathur and Sharma employed the electrodeless Tesla discharge in order to investigate the Tesla-luminiscence spectra of bromine, iodine and some organic substances and some of their results have already been communicated to the *Philosophical Magazine*.

While examining the Tesla-luminiscence spectra of organic substances, it was noticed by Bhatnagar and his colleagues that there existed a close similarity in the spectra of phenanthrene and anthracene, also of menthol and camphor. This led them to suspect that some sort of a chemical transformation might be going on in the discharge tube and this similarity observed might be due to the common part of the molecule obtained as a result of the decomposition of the substances examined. Further it was noticed that when at the end of the experiment the tube was taken out for cleaning, the product left behind was quite different in colour from the one originally taken. Evidently it seemed to have undergone some chemical change due to the electrodeless discharge. Reference to this has already been made in the Presidential Address of the Chemistry Section in the Fifteenth Session of the Indian Science Congress held at Calcutta in January, 1928, by one of us (S. S. B.).

In the present investigation an account has been presented of the attempts made to identify the compound obtained from naphthalene.

It will be of interest to recall some of the previous work on the subject. McVicker, Marsh and Stewart (*loc. cit.*) examined a large number of organic substances including naphthalene but they did not find in any case a chemical change taking place. They noticed, however, while examining the Tesla-luminiscence spectra of benzene, that particles of carbon got deposited in the Tesla tube and that the benzene was charred. These workers, however, did not employ the

electrodeless discharge and heated the substance in order to vaporize them.

While the present investigation was in progress there appeared in an issue of the *Chemistry and Industry* (March 23, 1928) the report of the Thirteenth Annual Guthrie Lecture of the Physical Society, London, delivered by Sir J. J. Thomson. In his lecture he introduced to the notice of the audience—

- (a) a new photo-electric effect,
- (b) a method of obtaining the "Heaviside layer",
- (c) a new method of synthesis.

Regarding (c) he found "that ordinary magnesium oxide combined with oxygen in the discharge tube to form a new oxide. Enquiry amongst his chemical friends had failed to elicit any information as to the known existence of this new oxide but he was informed by a chemical manufacturer that he manufactured a hundred-weight of it weekly. Calcium oxide and zinc oxide can be similarly oxidised in the discharge tube to form higher oxides. The rate of combination can be readily observed being metrical, and this new method was strongly recommended to the attention of the chemists as one offering every prospect of a means of effecting all sorts of combinations. Amongst all the substances he had tried, "helium" was the only one he had failed to oxidise.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The apparatus for obtaining the electrodeless discharge is the same as described in the paper communicated to the *Philosophical Magazine*. It consisted of a dental X-ray transformer, the primary of which was fed by an A. C. current. The secondary was connected to the primary of a Tesla coil, with a condenser and a spark gap in parallel to the Tesla. The secondary of the Tesla was connected to the ends of a solenoid covering the outer surface of the discharge tube, which consisted of a hard glass tube 25 cms. long. One end of it was finely ground where a quartz or glass plate could be cemented on or removed, as desired. The other end was suitably narrowed to take a thick rubber tubing joint. Evacuation was done by means of a Cenco-Hyvac pump and between this and the discharge tube, a wash-bottle was included to catch the organic vapours.

The discharge tube was thoroughly cleaned and dried and a thin layer of the substance was spread on its inner surface, after which the quartz plate was cemented on. All the joints were sealed with

Everett's vacuum wax to prevent leakage. The substance chosen was an extra pure sample of Merck's naphthalene freshly resublimed. It was exposed to the action of the discharge for three hours in course of which the tube was occasionally shaken to expose fresh layers. Prolonged exposures carbonized the sample completely and a greater quantity of the substance at one instance did not help much to increase the yield. So the tube had to be exposed a number of times. The glow obtained ranged from bluish violet to yellowish white. When the exposure is finished, it was always found that a portion of the substance got carbonized and the substance changed colour from white to yellowish brown. Most of it was removed by scrubbing while the portion that was carbonized could only be washed out by chloroform and stuck to the walls of the tube as a resinous matter.

The substance thus obtained was drained on a porous plate and left overnight to remove the gummy matter. It was then refluxed several times with chloroform till the solvent ceased to give any colour on boiling. The residue left behind was mostly charred naphthalene and was discarded. From the filtrate the solvent was got back by distillation and the concentrated chloroform extract evaporated off on a watch glass whereby a brown crust was obtained, which did not give a sharp melting point as it ranged between 70°-80°. This stuff consisted of unchanged naphthalene together with a new compound that is formed.

Separation of the Compound.—The brown mass, which was soluble in chloroform and in hot benzene, was separated from naphthalene either by refluxing with hot alcohol or by steam distillation in which case naphthalene got easily removed. The brownish black residue left after steam distillation was then boiled with alcohol in order to remove further quantities of naphthalene. The substance thus obtained on drying did not melt even at 300°.

Purification of the Substance.—It was further purified on refluxing with animal charcoal in chloroform solution to remove all the colouring and resinous matter present. The solution was then carefully filtered to remove the fine suspension of charcoal and the bulk was concentrated by distilling off the liquid. It was then dropped in excess of ether, when a heavy brown precipitate was obtained. This also did not melt even at 350°, but near about 300° the substance turned black, and shrinking of the mass took place.

Analysis of the Compound.—Qualitative analysis showed only the presence of carbon and hydrogen in the compound, which could be

detected by the usual tests for the elements. It burnt with a smoky flame and left no residue on the platinum foil when heated on it. Tests for the detection of groups failed to give any definite information. No addition product of any sort could be obtained. It was, however, completely soluble in chloroform and benzene, but very slightly in ether and alcohol and partly in acetone. Yield is very low, about 1 to 2 per cent. at the most on the above conditions.

Quantitative estimations were made of the elements present in the compound and the result of the combustion experiment was as follows :—

0.1050 gm. of the substance gave 0.3413 gm. of CO_2 and 0.0596 gm. of H_2O .

Therefore, Carbon = 88.64, Hydrogen = 6.30, Oxygen = 5.06 per cent. (by difference).

The molecular weight of the compound was determined by the cryoscopic method and found to be 318.

The empirical formula calculated on the strength of the combustion experiment comes to $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}$ and the molecular weight calculated according to this would be 324. The difference between the two values was, however, within the experimental errors. Hence the resulting compound obtained from naphthalene exposing the same to electrodeless discharge, has got the composition $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}$. Further work on the determination of the constitution of the compound is in progress.

It has also been observed that the following substances decompose in the manner shown against them, when exposed to the Tesla discharge :

PbSO_4 changes to PbSO_3 and PbS
 CaSO_4 " " CaSO_3
 KBrO_3 " " KBrO and KBr
 KIO_3 " " KI and I_2
 KClO_3 " " KClO and KCl .
 $\text{PbSO}_4 + \text{Mg}$ gives $\text{PbS} + \text{MgO}$.

Quantitative measurements will be communicated shortly.

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